

may not be high enough to lead to chemical reaction and obtains the relation

$$\frac{d \log K \text{ (velocity const.)}}{dT} = \frac{\bar{E} - \bar{E}}{kT^2}$$

where $\bar{E}$ is the average energy before activation of those molecules only which pick up radiant energy and react, and $\bar{E}$ is the average energy of all the molecules. If $\bar{E} - \bar{E}$ is zero, the temperature co-efficient is unity but if $\bar{E} - \bar{E}$ has a large value, the temperature co-efficient will be correspondingly large.

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DACCA.

Varying Valency of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles.

Part II.

BY

SIR PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY

AND

KSHITISH CHANDRA BOSE RAY.

It has already been shown that platinum in relation to certain mercaptanic radicles behaves as di-, tri-, tetra-, penta-, hexa- and octa-valent respectively (Ray *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 133). In the present communication further evidence is brought forward in support of this view.

Tri-, Tetra- and Penta-valent Platinum.

The product of the interaction of ethyl disulphide and platinum chloride, namely, $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2\text{PtCl}$ has already been described (*loc. cit.*) in which the platinum has been assigned penta-valency. Determination of the molecular weight in chloroform has now led us to treble the empirical formula; platinum would thus function as tri- or penta-valent:

It will be seen that the second compound is a nine-membered ring in the formation of which platinum takes part. Both the rings also conform to the sulphonium type (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 131, 603; 1917, 111, 101, etc.). By the interaction of sodium dithioethylene glycol and platinum chloride in acetone, derivatives of the mercaptan have been obtained in which platinum functions as tetra- and penta-valent respectively, thus:

and

The motive of the reaction evidently lies in the affinity of sulphur for the metal, in other words, the latter readily parts with its halogen atoms in preference to the sulphur.

Interaction of thylsulphide and Platinum Chloride.

As early as 1853 Loir described the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{PtCl}_4$ which he obtained by the interaction of the above (*Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1853, 39 [iii], 441). We have

recently undertaken a thorough and systematic investigation of the above reaction and have been able to isolate the following products of reaction: (a) $\text{Et}_2\text{S}, \text{PtCl}_2$; (b) $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2, \text{PtCl}_2$; (c) $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2, \text{PtCl}_3$; (d) $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2, \text{PtCl}_4$ and (e) $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2, \text{PtCl}_5$. The compound (b) has been obtained in six different isomeric modifications. One form, m. p. 77° , has already been described (Rây, *loc. cit.*). Two isomers with m. ps. 81° and 106° have been isolated by Blomstrand (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1888 [ii], 38, 352) both of which on further purification was shown by Tschugaeff and Malschewsky (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 135, 385) to possess the identical m. p., namely, 108° . These two varieties appear to be identical with the compounds (a) and (γ) described below. Three more isomers with m. ps. 108° , 104° and 96° respectively have also been obtained. The various isomers differ distinctly in physical properties, such as colour, crystalline form, melting point and solubility. In one and the same reaction two, three or more products are often simultaneously formed but the predominance of the one over the others is determined by the temperature at which the reaction is carried on as also by the active mass of the reactants. With the exception of (e) these compounds may be arranged in the following order in which the affinity value of platinum continuously varies from tri- to octa-valency, thus:

But the existence of the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{PtCl}_5$ would apparently land us in difficulty and is, in fact, a

stumbling block in the path of the acceptance of the above method of representation of the valency of platinum, which would assign (*c*) hepta- and (*e*) ennea-valency. The following alternative mode of representation therefore naturally suggests itself :—

which would make platinum in (*c*) and (*e*) tri- and penta-valent respectively and sulphur tetravalent. This view of the constitution brings it into line with that proposed for $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2, 2\text{AuCl}_2$ in which the compound has been shown to belong to the sulphonium series (Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 64). But a better method would be to explain their constitution according to Werner's theory. As for the different modifications of $(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2, \text{PtCl}_2$ the existence of three isomers can be explained in the following way :

- (1) Blomstrand's *cis*-compound;
- (2) Blomstrand's *trans*-compound;
- (3) $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4] \text{PtCl}_2$.

(*c*) may be represented as a molecular compound of (*b*) and (*d*): $[(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_3\text{PtCl}_2] [(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{PtCl}_4]$ or $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4]\text{PtCl}_2$ (*cf.* Tschugaeff, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 82, 420). In fact on crystallisation from boiling alcohol, it breaks up into the two component molecules. (*e*) is constituted according to the scheme—

An aqueous solution of (e) turns blue litmus red, thus showing the acidic structure of the compound. This view of the constitution of these compounds receives further support from the facts that the following reaction takes place on treating (b) m. p. 96° and m. p. 104° with ammonia :

The ammonia-substituted compound has been found to precipitate the whole of its chlorine in aqueous solution with silver nitrate as silver chloride. Both the chlorine atoms are therefore outside the co-ordination ring. (c) when similarly treated with ammonia is converted into $\text{PtCl}_2, \text{Et}_2\text{S}, 4\text{NH}_3$. That the chlorine atoms in these compounds are not equally ionised in solution is proved by the conductivity experiments appended below as also by those made by Tschugaeff and Malschewsky (*loc. cit.*) Further work in this line is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Interaction of Disodium Dithioethyleneglycol and Platinic Chloride.—(a) The disodium compound was suspended in ether and solid platinic chloride was added. On being refluxed for a few hours a light brick-red precipitate was obtained, which was washed repeatedly with water till the filtrate was completely free from chlorine.

Found: Pt=43.93; S=29.14. $\text{Pt} \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{II} \\ \text{Cl}_2 \\ \text{IV} \\ \text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2) \end{array} \right], (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}$

or $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2, \text{PtCl}_2, (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}^*$ requires Pt=43.44 and S=28.22 per cent.

* Cf. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 79, foot-note.

(b) The disodium derivative was suspended in anhydrous acetone and an acetone solution of platinic chloride mixed with it. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for about an hour. A chocolate-coloured precipitate was obtained which was repeatedly extracted with boiling nitrobenzene in order to remove ethylene disulphide, which is produced simultaneously and which is deposited as a flocculent precipitate when the solvent cools down. The precipitate was finally washed with boiling alcohol

and ether. It had the composition $2\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2$.^{IV} (Found: Pt=46.11; S*=35.00. Theory requires Pt=46.13 and S=37.50 per cent. Chlorine was found to be absent). When the same preparation was repeated by refluxing the mixture on the water bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, a precipitate was obtained which was purified by a method similar to that described above. The compound had the composition $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2) = \text{Pt} = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)$. (Found: Pt=49.61; C=12.43; H=2.40; S=33.73. Theory requires Pt=51.71; C=12.60; H=2.10 and S=33.60 per cent.) As platinic chloride is very sparingly soluble in ether the reaction was not completed in the sense that one atom of chlorine remained attached to the metal in the final product of the reaction; whereas, when acetone was used as the menstruum in which platinic chloride is readily soluble the reaction went much further and the whole of the chlorine was removed.

Interaction of Diethylsulphide and Platinic Chloride.—

(a) Excess of aqueous chloroplatinic acid and ethylsulphide were heated in a sealed tube at 160° — 70° for 15 hours. On cooling, a treacle-like substance settled at the bottom of the tube; it was separated from the supernatant

* As the sulphur was estimated by fusion with a mixture of sodium carbonate and potassium nitrate a small quantity of it escaped as sulphone. Hence the p. c. was found to be a little low (*vide infra*, foot-note, p. 185).

aqueous layer, dissolved in acetone and precipitated by alcohol. A brick-red product which did not melt up to 250° was obtained. It was further purified by crystallisation from a very concentrated solution in chloroform. (Found : Pt=61.75 ; Cl=11.18. $(C_2H_5)_2SPtCl$ requires Pt=61.09 and Cl=11.00 per cent). The acetone-alcoholic mother-liquor on evaporation gave a semi-solid mass which was repeatedly dissolved in chloroform and precipitated by ether. The crop of crystals thus yielded had the m. p. 108° (*vide infra*).

(*b*) Ethyl sulphide in excess and an aqueous solution of platinic chloride were mixed up in a sealed tube and heated in a steam-jacket for 5 hours. The aqueous supernatant layer was filtered off and allowed to evaporate spontaneously. The residue was treated with boiling alcohol and the solution filtered off. The filtrate on cooling deposited a crop of golden-yellow plates, m. p. 108° (*a*). (Found : Pt=44.50 ; Cl=16.47. $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_2$ requires Pt=43.97 and Cl=15.85 per cent.). The mother-liquor was allowed to evaporate. The residue was dissolved in hot benzene, which on cooling yielded a crop of pale white crystals, m. p. 108° (*b*). The aqueous layer described above on slow evaporation deposited pale greenish yellow crystals, m. p. 110° (*c*). Though the compounds (*a*) and (*b*) had identical m. p. 108° they differed widely in physical properties such as colour, solubility and evidently crystalline form. This is quite in keeping with the constitution assigned to them according to Werner's theory as discussed above. All the varieties were analysed and were found to have the identical composition.

(*e*) Excess of ethylsulphide and solid platinic chloride were mixed in a test-tube and continuously stirred for about an hour. A pasty mass was obtained, which was treated with a few c.c. of water. The aqueous extract was removed by filtration. The pasty

mass was washed with alcohol so as to remove the unacted-upon ethylsulphide. The yellow residue was repeatedly washed with benzene till all the soluble impurities were removed. A bright orange-red crystalline mass was obtained, m. p. 109°. It had the composition $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_3$. (Found: Pt=41.47; Cl=22.09 and S* = 11.59. $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_3$ requires Pt=40.75; Cl=22.03 and S=13.24 per cent.). This product is evidently a 'molecular' compound made up of equimolecular proportions of (b) and (d), thus:

On crystallisation from boiling alcohol it yields a copious precipitate of (d). The mother-liquor on slow evaporation yields as first crop a mixture of (b) and (d) and the final crop is pure (b), m. p. 78°. The compound (d) had been prepared by another method and described in a previous communication (Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 140). On repeating the method of preparation described by Loir (*loc. cit.*) an orange-yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained. The French chemist described it as melting at 108° but the preparation, even on being repeated several times, was found to melt at 113°. Loir did not analyse this compound but thought—*erroneously*, as it is now found—that it could be further purified by crystallisation from boiling alcohol. By this process he only recovered the compound $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_4$ whose m. p.

* Great difficulty was experienced in estimating the sulphur of the present series of compounds. Carius' method followed by fusion with KNO_3 and Na_2CO_3 yielded negative results. The reason was that the Et_2S was thereby converted into the sulphone Et_2SO_2 . When the contents of the tube were washed out and evaporated to remove the excess of nitric acid, the sulphone volatilised with the steam and thus sulphur could not be estimated by this method. The nitric acid in Carius' method was therefore supplemented by the addition of bromine. The excess of bromine and nitric acid was subsequently evaporated off and the residue fused as usual with KNO_3 and Na_2CO_3 . Even this method gave the p. c. of sulphur slightly low.

he did not determine after recrystallisation. Evidently, the original compound $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_2$ broke up into its two components as shown above during the crystallisation.

(d) Ethylsulphide² and an excess of an aqueous solution of platinic chloride were taken in a sealed tube and heated at 100° for 9 hours. On cooling, a yellow crystalline deposit was found at the bottom of the tube over which there was a layer of shining, colourless needle-shaped crystals. The tube was cut open and the two kinds of crystals filtered off from the aqueous mother-liquor, separated mechanically and pressed between the folds of a filter-paper to remove the adhering mother-liquor. The colourless variety had the m. p. 104° and the composition $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_2$ (δ). Evidently it was the fourth isomer of the compounds (α), (β) and (γ) described above. (Found: Pt = 44.35; Cl = 16.40 per cent.). The yellow crystals were purified by solution in hot alcohol, which on cooling deposited yellow needle-shaped crystals, m. p. 198° . This was identical with the compound (d). From the alcoholic mother-liquor of this product on spontaneous evaporation two sets of crystals were obtained: (i) lemon-yellow monoclinic plates, the crystallography of which is given below, and (ii) orange-yellow ill-defined needles. (i) was mechanically separated from (ii) and twice recrystallised from alcohol. This compound is the fifth isomer having the composition $(Et_2S)_2PtCl_2$, m. p. 96° (ϵ). (Molecular weight by the cryoscopic method in benzene = 336.3. Theory requires M.W. = 347.) The ebullioscopic method of M.W. determination in benzene gave anomalous results. Evidently some sort of molecular rearrangement takes place. (ii) was too minute in quantity to allow of purification and analysis. The aqueous mother-liquor in the above reaction was concentrated by slow evaporation over strong sulphuric acid whereby yellow crystals of a

mixture of $(Et_3S)_2PtCl_3$ and $(Et_3S)_2PtCl_4$ were obtained. These were filtered off and the mother-liquor further concentrated till no more yellow crystals were yielded. At this stage the filtrate, which became very small in bulk, was transferred to a lime-desiccator to remove HCl which began to evolve. Beautiful orange needle-shaped crystals began to separate out, which were further purified by redissolving in minute quantity of water. On repeating the process the pure crystals thus obtained were found to melt at 90° . They had the composition $(Et_3S)_2PtCl_3 \cdot 2H_2O$. (Found: Pt=33.96; Cl=30.42. Theory requires Pt=33.57 and Cl=30.06 per cent.)

Molecular Weight of $Et_3S_nPtCl_m$.—Ebullioscopic determination of the molecular weight in chloroform gave M.W.=942. $(Et_3S)_2PtCl_3$ requires M.W.=1093.5.

Conductivity of $(Et_3S)_2PtCl_3$ in Acetone Solution at 23° .

Concentration in gm. mols.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^{-9}$ (freshly prepared solution).	Sp. conductivity $\times 10^{-9}$ (after keeping the solution for 1 day).
0.01036	25.2	28.8
0.00618	12.2	14.8
0.00345	...	8.8

Conductivity of the Above at 30° .

Concentration in gm. mols.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^{-9}$ (freshly prepared solution).	Sp. cond. $\times 10^{-9}$ (after keeping for 1 day).	Sp. cond. $\times 10^{-9}$ (after keeping for 4 days).
0.0177	2.7	9.9	39.4
0.00885	...	4.6	20.0
0.00442	...	...	9.0
0.00221	...	6.1	19.2
0.00221	...	1.008	...

That the chlorine atoms are non-ionisable is afforded by the fact that on adding silver nitrate solution very slight precipitate of AgCl is obtained; but on shaking the mixture from day to day, the quantity of the latter goes on increasing. At the end of a fortnight complete precipitation is secured.

Crystallography of (d), m. p. 198°.

The crystals belong to monoclinic system, holohedral class.

Habit: (1) Pseudo-hexagonal, tabular on the clinopinacoid and also (2) stout prismatic

The following combination of forms is observed:—

(001)	...	...	...	Base
(010)	...	...	...	Clinopinacoid
(100)	...	...	...	Orthopinacoid
(110)	...	...	...	Unit prisms
(101)	...	...	...	Orthodome

Cleavage absent, conchoidal fracture: Highly brittle.

Optical Properties: Anisotropic, fairly strong double refraction with moderate interference colours. Feebly pleochroic. Extinction oblique. Ext. $\angle$ 12°—14° on C-axis.

Crystallography of (ε), m. p. 96°.

The crystal belongs to the normal or holohedral class of the monoclinic system.

It has a pinacoidal habit—tabular on the orthopinacoid.

The following faces are the only ones present:—

Orthopinacoid	...	...	... (100)
Clinodome	...	...	... (011)
Unit prism	...	...	... (110)
Unit pyramid	...	...	... (111)

Cleavage planes totally absent. Fracture conchoidal.
Highly brittle.

Optically:—It is faintly pleochroic; the pleochroism is olive-green to brownish green.

Anisotropic, with fairly high birefringence.

Extinction oblique—extinction $\angle$ on the *C*-axis is 10° — 11° .

No twinning present. Optically biaxial.

The crystal faces though fully developed, possess too imperfectly formed surfaces for goniometric treatment. Hence measurement of crystal angles and axes is impossible with such a crystal.

It is to be regretted that the crystals of the six modifications of $(Et_3S)_2PtCl_2$ were either of a mealy character or imperfectly developed. Only the (ϵ), m. p. 96° , could be obtained in a fairly perfect form. The compound (d) yielded, on slow evaporation from acetone solution, well-developed crystals.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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